

The underwater heritage of Santa Catarina Island (Praia dos Ingleses), Brazil: A digital pedagogical game

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Abstract

With this paper we intend to present the underwater archaeology project designed to study and examine the heritage submerged in Santa Catarina Island (Florianopolis, Brazil), its aims, methodologies and expected outcomes.

Underwater archaeology is a very recent discipline in which there still are a lot of gaps to be filled as far as the study and understanding of submerged property is concerned.

Despite the competent authorities' efforts, there is still a lot to discover about the hidden history in oceans and rivers.

In Brazil, the scenario is even more critical especially in what concerns the understanding of colonization, the different historical events and settlements by European peoples.

The Instituto Politécnico de Tomar and PAS, which since 2004, has been undertaking underwater surveys in this region in collaboration with other renowned organizations, are joining efforts to develop an archaeological/historical project in this area. The project will cover investigations in the frontal area of Praia dos Ingleses, located in the Northeastern part of Santa Catarina Island, Florianopolis, Brasil, but in a further stage it may extend to the whole coast.

The primary goal of this project is to recognise the archaeological remains submerged in this region, thus contributing to a better understanding of naval history, material culture, artefact conservation, nautical technology, the maritime economy in pre- and post-colonial times and above all the development of a digital database associated to a GIS system, which will allow effective record and mapping of the heritage identified in the course of surveying and excavation works. As well as these scientific aims, the project is also intended to develop strategies of management, preservation and tourist enhancement. To this effect, we plan to produce 3D and audiovisual contents for a more attractive dissemination of the findings and also develop a plan for the creation of a local museum.

Keywords: underwater archaeology, project, pedagogical game.

1. Introduction

Underwater archaeology is a very recent discipline in which there still are a lot of gaps to be filled as far as the study and understanding of submerged property is concerned. Sought after for its natural wealths, Brazil has been the stage for many attacks and explorations by the Portuguese and foreign peoples in their quest for raw materials and exotic products. Historical unawareness seems to be critical in the South where Praia dos Ingleses is located (Florianópolis).

In the framework of a partnership with Instituto Politécnico de Tomar (IPT) and Projecto de Arqueologia

Subaquática (PAS), an archaeological-historical survey project of the area is proposed (FIGUEIREDO et al. 2010). The contribution of Portuguese team was presented to the Fundação Ciências e Tecnologia (FCT) to be financed, but part of the works are carried out with own funding involved institutions.

In this region (Figure 1) a wrecked vessel has been discovered which is not yet identified, but the artifacts found inside allows it to be dated to 1687 (Figure 2 and 3). It was right around this time that Portuguese settlements occurred in this region; these remains may well have a connection with their activities in this location.

So far archaeological survey in the cove has found no more remains from the colonial period. Thus, the study

of this wrecked is essential to understanding this area during this period.

Figure 1: Image of Praia dos Ingleses where was found the wreck.

2. State of art

Although some general bibliographic references on Brazilian settlements are known, references to *Santa Catarina* Island and *Praia dos Ingleses* are very scarce; So the data obtained are more related with the field evidences. The following remarks can be made:

- The coastline of the island offered shelter and food to several maritime routes; this vessel may therefore be connected with a variety of historic contexts.

- Vessel construction techniques suggest a Spanish origin, probably a Brigantine.

From international bibliography, there is evidence that, during this period, at least 262 boats harboured or sailed off the Island's shore and 5 wrecked between Parana and Buenos Aires but none of them occurred in the vicinity of the island (NOELLI, et al. 2009). Despite the scarce bibliographic references the PAS team are making some advances to identify the wrecked. One of the first clues was made in Coelho publications (1856:184) in it says that "this beach is called *Praia dos Ingleses* because an English ship wrecked off this coast in ancient times of which some vestiges or even remains have been found during the storm of March 1838". This is the only reference to it in the historic records of the island.

The historian Amilcar D'Avila de Mello (2005), one of the foremost experts in the colonial history of Santa Catarina suggested the hypothesis that the vessel belongs to Thomas Frinz, possibly sunk in 1687. The main source of information is the Nobiliarquia Paulistana, of 1980, when Pedro de Almeida Taques, transcribed parts of the Frins log book, made by the Portuguese courts in Santos on 1688, hypothesis that is also confirm by two English pirates chroniclers William Dampier, in 1702 and Raveneau de Lussan, in 1689 (NOELLI et al. 2009), that says that Thomaz Frins was an English pirate, sailing with seven Englishmen, in a Brigantine (that is the founded vessel type); It was from England to Porto Belo, Panama; Belonged to the fleet of small ships of nine undred men, commanded by "Samoloy" (probably the

captains Swan and Townley, crew of Edward Davis pirate force); "They went as pirates, plundering the lands of the Spanish crown: Panama, Callao, Porto Santo, Peru, Chile; The Frins boat separated from the fleet in the vicinity of Callao; Was "six months" looking for the rest of the fleet; Carrying wine (the remains allowed to recovered a several ceramic bowls for one bushel); In Porto Santo have a battle war with spanish and the boat was very damage, surviving Frins and seven men; In need of repairs and water, cliffs in N^a Sr^a do Desterro, that is today Florianópolis; and were prisoner of Francisco Dias Velho, in 1687, that was the governor of this Portuguese colony, exactly in the time of the wreck dated.

One more coincidence was reported by Lussan, in 1689, that in one meeting of a French group, in April 1687, near Sta Helena, with a big Spanish ship commanded by the British, indicates that the boat had been captured by English pirates at the time of Nazca, carrying wine and corn and was piloted by a small crew of eight men. Also he says that they were looking for the others ships.

The recovered rudder has 6.7 m in height which is possible to estimate a large Spanish brigantine stolen by Frins group, with more than 22 m in length (Figure 2).

Figure 2 and 3: Drawing of tiller recovered and photomosaic of the wreck remains

So we start to be some assurance that is the Thomas Frins Pirate Brigantine.

3. Methodology

According to the summary presented, different activities will be carried out in the framework of institutional partnerships by the interdisciplinary team. In summary, the workplan for this project includes execution of three basic components of the underwater archaeological study:

1. Survey and record of all documental data and bibliographic references related with Santa Catarina Island allowing understanding the dynamics, contacts and influences in this region across history.

2. Intensive surveying around the island and GIS mapping of all structures and anomalies detected:
3. Survey and excavation (Figure 4 and 5) of the known vessel in an endeavour to identify and recover the greater amount of data. This stage will comprise computer processing, preservation and restoration of recovered materials and a detailed study of exhumed remains.

Figure 4: Diver in an excavation work

Figure 5: Image of excavation work

These three components will lead to further generation of didactic and pedagogic contents which, in conjunction with recovered artefacts and structures, will be duly exhibited at the local Museum. Some of this contents have the aim to sensitize the public for the protection of underwater heritage and create a better understand of the archaeological works and the found remains. So movies, 3d reconstructions (Figure 6) and games are made to try to make a shorter links with the layman public.

Figure 6: Two different 3D reconstruction objects: a sundial and a tin fountain.

4. The pedagogical game

One of the contents that we are working one leads us directly with the possible wreck identification and the history of vessel life. To try to pass it to the public and taking consideration the younger one, we start to work in a pedagogical game connecting all the information's knowed until now. Our aim was try to justify the presence of some recovered objects and give them some history life. Like this all the objects get some importance in the game and are the connection inter-scenes. The first step was to select the objects recovered to use in the game. So, from the history of the Thomas Frinz and the archaeological finds we have some interesting material that can lead us to some places of passage trip and are essential to understand the remains

4.1. The real history: What we know?

In the archaeological works was found "material evidence from the Pacific coast of north-western, South and Central America, with coincide with the pirates routes in question"(NOELLI, et al. 2009) also was recollected some important object that could date the vessel.

One of the artefacts is a english Gunter scale, dated from 1683, the time of the depart of English crew. Another object is a "metate" that is used in Central America to produce corn flour (one of the type products that the chronics documents says that Thomas Frinz transported) and a clue from the passage for this sites. Another interesting thing is a fossil shell fragment (*Concholepas concholepas* Martyn) that is a mollusc of the family *Muricidae* appreciated as food, from the southern Peru to southern Chile, and could be part of crew food when they pass to this location. Moreover was recovered some coral beads that was related with this indigenous features. About the ceramic material were recovered more than 11 000 pieces of bottles of one bushel, of type Form 1 (James 1988), used to transport and store wine, oil, water, grains etc. For the PAS team the wide variety of sizes and type of clay matches with the information that the strength pirate looted bottles of wine and water in various locations and boats in Central and South American coasts. Among the objects recovered account is still a thimble, an ink cartridge in with the coat of tin Habsburgs; a knife, a bell and a sundial. The sundial displays the coordinates pointing to the Canary Islands to the north and the River Plate to the south, be the possible route of the vessel (PAS, 2006). From the remains it was also found different human bones and the rudder presented partly carbonized, with could indicate some fire episode.

4.2. The fiction and the connection with the history data

Our aim was construct a three level game. The first dedicate to the possibly history of Thomas Frinz pirate,

represented the history that the documents present and explain the wreck, making some fiction scenes about some recovered objects; the second level is dedicate to the archaeological underwater works, the public will be related with archaeological methodology problems, recovering the objects, the same that we take to inside of the vessel in the first level; the third level deals with the lab works to preserving and restoration the artefacts, give them is original appearance. Like this, with this pedagogical content we can explain the objects history life that the younger people can see in the museum, understanding for what was the objects used, the transformation of the material after the wreck, with the time passage and what was the process to recovered until the appearance that they have in the exposition (ex. Figure 7).

Figure 7: Cannonball before and after the restoration intervention.

We know that Thomas Frinz was English, so the game's story starts in England in the infancy of this character. In a meeting with his grandfather, also dedicated to the art of sailing and piracy, in a scene who would dictate his fate as a pirate, Thomas's grandfather gives him a treasure map and some objects.

Thomas grows with the intention of following his grandfather footsteps and when adult became part of Samoloy crew. With others depart for Spanish colonies, in Central America. Along the way several challenges will happen, making add to his bag some objects, that will after subsequently be recovered by the archaeological team. In this challenges is created a history for the sundial, to the Gunter scale, to the wine bottles etc.

However he also becomes counter-master and after a few failed attacks, as in a situation where the boat suffer some damage, start looking for his companion and heads in N^a Sr^a do Desterro, the place were his grandfather told him that he hide the treasure. In that site was prisoner by Francisco Dias Velho and his vessel wrecked.

This will link to the second level were the wreck was found and start the archaeological works. In this we will ask to the player to dig the wreck and extract the object to the surfer, of course using all king of archaeological techniques and taking in account the diver equipment.

Each time that they found something we will remember the Thomas Frinz history and reconstruct by the present to the past, all the data, and get more clues about the treasure. In the third level the player will enter in a lab and will work on the objects recovered with the aim to get the real appearance. With this level he will understand the difficulty and the methodology need to conserve an object, will join products, making the desalination, taking x-ray, etc. until the final stage, in some of them they will collect more and more data that lead the player until the treasure chest. To open it have to answer some questions and remember all the scenes.

5. Conclusion

At this moment we are working in the first level, trying to leave open as much as possible the story to add new information that however may be collected. For better generalization of the game is being developed in Flash CS4, allowing it to be played on any computer, easily downloaded, not occupy much space and brief to be used in any classroom or be exposed in a museum.

The research and study will continue towards a precise identification of the vessel and they may even come to change the history of this script.

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